

**LEVELS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF
PERSONAL AND CREATIVE COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS**

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Annotation: The following article focuses on the implementation of a competent approach to the formation of personal-creative competencies in students, the identification and selection of personal-creative competencies are determined by the main consumers of learning outcomes and what skills and qualities are valued in society today.

Keywords: potential, innovation, competent approach, skills, investment, ethical requirements, personal-creative competencies

INTRODUCTION

It is known that all the work being done in the world today to develop education is considered an investment in the future. The introduction of mechanisms to increase the effectiveness of the development of personal and creative competencies in students in our society creates opportunities for all people to live in a comfortable environment through education, vocational training, a worthy contribution to the development of the country.

After gaining independence, our country has given priority to radically improving the structure and content of the development of personal and creative competencies in secondary education, especially among students. The problem of formation of personal-creative competencies in students is solved on the basis of different approaches to knowledge of language, vocabulary and speech culture in modern methodological literature. There are examples of the use of a new term in

official documents on the consistency of reforms in our country, for example, "Strategy for modernization of the content of general education" as follows:

The level of competence-oriented, as well as the separation from the old educational paradigm, the main criteria of which are knowledge, skills and abilities, ensures the preservation of BCM as one of the necessary elements of the educational process

MAIN PART

Based on the comparison of the above ideas and their generalization on the principal cases, it is possible to distinguish three views on the definition of competencies and competencies and the establishment of meaningful connections between them. At first glance, the idea is typical: competence is impersonal, it is a set of norms, requirements, qualities, a specific qualification description of the specialist. Its task is to determine what a person, an expert, a student needs to know to do in a particular situation and in a particular place. It can be assigned appropriate levels, categories that represent the complexity of the problems to be solved or the types of work to be performed. Competence As an existing quality of a person with the competence being studied in this case, he or she will have a private local character. For example, if we are talking about the acquisition of multiple competencies for any professional activity, then competence serves as an integrative quality and is called professional competence.

The next view expands the concept of "competence" and includes in its scope the final requirements for the functions acquired by man, but also the mental, physiological, axiological, social, functional structures that are formed in it. Only then will competencies acquire a position of competence, as their objective content becomes a subjective image of personal qualities. The second point of view differs from the first only in the broader interpretation of the concept of "competence". According to the latter view, competencies can only be said to be related to their readiness and ability to solve specific problems and tasks, while competence is seen as a complex description that testifies to a person's acquisition of a number of competencies in a particular field. The concept of private and local competencies

loses its meaning in this case. Subsequent studies will rely on a second perspective. According to him, the phrase "personal-creative competencies" is not only relevant, but also the content of educational activities.

A well-known educator, A.V. Related to Khutorsky's view, competence is the formation and development of competencies in which a person has the appropriate competence, and the purpose of higher education is a hierarchical structure.

There are many attempts to give a meaningful meaning to the term “competence”. An analysis of successful and less successful opinions on the subject encourages us to be convinced of the need for the debate to continue and to offer our own option.

We define competence as a systematic set of subject awareness, skills, meaningful orientation, adaptive capabilities, work experience, and methods of obtaining a specific product in the objects and processes of a particular classroom environment. Competence is generally understood as a set of certain norms, requirements for the quality of the process and its results within a meaningful part of a particular activity phase. He is impersonal and multi-factorial. On the one hand, it represents a certain set of factors that determine the quality of work performed, and on the other - can determine the quantitative scale for each factor takes

Unlike a number of authors, we would not have linked these descriptions only to a person’s time in an educational institution. In an environment where the idea of lifelong learning takes the form of a cultural norm and forms the basis of a new educational paradigm, the learning process goes beyond specific institutions, fixed-term boundaries, and clearly defined learning periods. The open education model is entering higher education institutions, the first sign of which is the legal externality at this stage of education. As a result of the above considerations, educational competence is defined by the expression given above in the disclosure of some general concepts to the general concept of ‘competence’.

Based on the results of the feedback, we obtain the following definition: Educational competence is the ability of a student to acquire a specific product in an

environment of model objects and processes embedded in the fields of study and academic disciplines. Bespalko included the following in his basic personal characteristics: social, existential, mental, biological. The minimum requirement ensures that the educational process can be carried out for the voluntary educational institution and the voluntary student. However, this requirement does not preclude voluntary high achievement where conditions exist (gifted students and skilled teachers). V.P. Bespalko gives a brief (annotated) description of the main characteristics of a person and their interpretation through the concept of personality traits. The structure of a person's social characteristics includes qualities such as a person's worldview, morals, aesthetics, and work ethic. It is the social characteristics of the individual that determine the most common behavior of man among people, in nature, his attitude to the processes taking place there and the degree of participation in them. Also, the existential characteristics of the individual determine the level of a person's readiness for life, its benefits to human society, its place and value in the developing socio-production processes. These qualities are in many ways determined by a person's well-being and his or her success in life. Thus, the structure of the existential characteristics of a person includes such qualities as his active experience, skills, consciousness, personality culture, his daily habits - which are valued and massly rewarded in a person in social recognition. Social and existential traits are acquired by an individual only as a result of organized reading and all possible interactions with people. They can vary throughout life depending on circumstances and education. It is clear from this that we have first identified a clear and understandable methodological framework, and the ability to adapt to itself and the surrounding reality is a guarantee of effective social existence that brings mutual satisfaction to man and society. Therefore, from now on we will rely on the basic educational competencies developed by us. The identification and selection of personal-creative competencies in students is determined by the main consumers of learning outcomes and depends on what abilities and qualities are currently valued in this society. But the logic of a competent approach is to actualize one or another

competence at each new stage of development of society. The individual-creative competencies offered in the context of an educational institution are formed by the whole lifestyle, the spirit of its educational environment, the content of curricula and the personal influence of the student body. Individual-creative competencies perform a methodological function. Subsequent detailed explanations of the requirements of this discipline are made in general and in science-specific competencies, and they serve as a specific methodological basis for the construction of curricula for individual disciplines or interdisciplinary cycles.

We have identified a clear and understandable methodological basis, and the ability to harmonize with oneself and the surrounding reality is a guarantee of effective social existence that brings mutual satisfaction to man and society. Therefore, from now on we will rely on personal-creative educational competencies developed by us. We know that the identification and selection of personal-creative competencies is determined by the main consumers of learning outcomes and depends on what skills and qualities are currently valued in this society. But the logic of a competent approach is to actualize one or another competence at each new stage of development of society. The individual-creative competencies offered in the context of an educational institution are formed by the whole way of life, the spirit of its educational environment, the content of curricula and the personal influence of the teaching staff. Individual-creative competencies perform a methodological function. Subsequent detailed explanations of the requirements of this discipline are made in general and in science-specific competencies, and they serve as a specific methodological basis for the construction of curricula for individual disciplines or interdisciplinary cycles. Like many researchers, we believe that the learning environment can be understood in a broader sense as an area of interaction of educational systems, their elements, educational material and subjects of educational processes. The need for an analysis of the characteristics of the learning environment is based on the fact that significant changes have taken place in the national educational environment, the predominance of sustainability has been

replaced by uncertainty. The uncertainty of the educational environment in Uzbekistan is the long-term process of reforming and modernizing the education system, as well as the changing social and state needs for education and its level.

CONCLUSION

Hence, the considered set of personal-creative competencies in students is in one respect reminiscent of each other, and in another they differ. The analysis of the set of competencies proposed by local and foreign scholars in the field of pedagogy shows that in the context of modern socio-economic requirements to the higher education system, students are encouraged to develop an author's collection of personal and creative competencies.

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